

DEFINITION OF THE CONCEPTS OF ANXIETY AND ANXIETY

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Abstract: *The article deals with the phenomena of anxiety and anxiety; definitions of foreign and domestic authors; dilution of the concepts of anxiety and anxiety.*

Keywords: *anxiety; anxiety; research; condition; feature.*

In the psychological scientific literature, one can find various definitions of the concept of anxiety and anxiety. Research in this area was carried out by both domestic and foreign scientists: Sigmund Freud, Anna Freud, A. M. Parishioner, Rollo May, Karen Horney, Charles Spielberger, A.S. Spivakovskaya and others.

The following definition is given in the psychological dictionary: Anxiety is an individual psychological feature that manifests itself in a person's predisposition to intense and frequent experiences of anxiety, as well as in a low threshold of its occurrence. It is considered as a personal education or as a property of temperament, which is due to the weakness of nervous processes.

According to A.M. Parishioners, anxiety is the experience of emotional discomfort, the appearance of a premonition of impending danger is an expression of dissatisfaction with significant human needs.

So S.L. Solovyova in her works notes that from a physiological point of view, anxiety is a reactive state. It causes physiological changes in the body that prepare the body for a fight – retreat, flight or resistance, attack, attack. With anxiety, blood pressure increases, the rhythm of heart contractions becomes more frequent, the activity of intestinal activity decreases, blood from the gastrointestinal tract is redistributed into the muscular system. Thus, the body prepares for active activity.

In the scientific psychological literature, two main phenomena can be found at the same time, which in some cases are used as synonyms, but are very often divorced as independent concepts: anxiety and anxiety.

For example, in English, anxiety and anxiety are denoted by one word - anxiety, and when reading foreign literature to dilute these concepts, you

need to pay attention to the context of their use. In Russian, these are different words, and you should pay attention to the difference between them. Anxiety is a state of anxiety that begins in a person in a situation that poses a certain physical or psychological threat to him. According to psychoanalytic theories, the state of anxiety is a useful adaptive mechanism that encourages an individual to defensive behavior to overcome danger. Anxiety, in turn, is an individual psychological feature that manifests itself in a person's tendency to often experience severe anxiety for relatively small reasons.

In the early works of Z. Freud , two variants of the explanation of anxiety are found: as a result of the discharge of suppressed sexual desire and as a signal of the presence of a dangerous situation, which requires an adequate adaptation from the individual.

A.V. Petrovsky and M. G. Yaroshevsky argue that the definition of anxiety as a state is basic, key to the definition of anxiety as a personality trait. That is, anxiety is "a person's predisposition to experiencing anxiety, characterized by a low threshold for the occurrence of an anxiety reaction."

I.V. Dubrovina in her works distinguishes the understanding of anxiety as an emotional state of a person, as its stable properties, personality traits or temperament, understanding anxiety as "the experience of emotional discomfort associated with the expectation of trouble, with a premonition of impending danger."

In turn, C.D. Spielberger distinguishes situational anxiety and personal anxiety. Personal anxiety is understood as a stable individual characteristic that reflects an individual's predisposition to anxiety and suggests that he has a tendency to perceive a wide range of situations as threatening, responding to each of them with a certain reaction. As a predisposition, personal anxiety is activated when certain stimuli are perceived by a person as dangerous to self-esteem, self-esteem.

Conclusion: The problem of anxiety and anxiety remains one of the main problems being developed in both foreign and domestic psychology. It seems important to separate the concepts of "anxiety" and "anxiety". Thus, it is fashionable to consider anxiety as a state of anxiety that occurs in situations that pose a threat to an individual. At the same time, anxiety, unlike anxiety, is an individual psychological feature of a person, manifested in the frequent experience of a state of severe anxiety in response to relatively weak stimuli in intensity.

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